

**SELECTION OF MODELS FOR NATIONAL SHIRTS AND TROUSERS,
MODELING, PREPARATION OF PATTERNS****Doniyorova Durdona Botir qizi**2 Vocational Vocational Schools, Zhargo`an District,
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Annotation: Making national dresses and modeling them is an important field. This article discusses the methodology of modeling national dress and trousers.

Keywords: national dress, trousers, pattern, model, technology.

INTRODUCTION

Modeling and sewing of national costumes is carried out using a unique technology. The main (avra) and derivative (lining) patterns for the shirt, and the main patterns for the dress are developed. (Table 1).

The main templates are developed for the collar, front, back yoke, hem (length), sleeve, and the bottom, derivative templates are developed for the front and back yoke. The order of construction and formalization of dress and skirt patterns 1 a, b, v - the values of seam allowances are given in table 2.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The templates are compared and coordinated according to the length and configuration of the connecting cuts. The pattern specification specifies the order and number of pieces included in one set of clothes. After the patterns are cut, they are formalized based on technical conditions: Marking marks are placed on each piece: garment name, size, height, piece name, number of cut pieces. In the patterns, the direction of the thread and the size of its permissible deviation, the lines indicating their minimum and maximum width in the places where the yoke falls, and control notches are clearly indicated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1.

Specification of national dress and necessary patterns

Section name	Symbol	Number		Symbol of symmetry
		in the template	in the blade	
Front coquette	01	1	2	+
Back coquette	02	1	1	-
Front piece hem	03	1	1	+
Back piece hem	04	1	1	+
Eat	05	1	2	+
Collar	06	1	2	+

Front lining	coquettish	07	1	2	-
Back lining	coquettish	08	1	1	+
Adip		09	1	2	+
Trousers		10	1	2	+
Trousers cuff		11	1	2	+

Note: "+" sign means a symmetrical part.

Certain rules must be followed for the more economical use of gas. For example, when making a pattern for cutting a garment with a flower facing one side or a feather, the patterns should be placed in such a way that even after the garment is sewn, the flowers or feathers on its pieces face the same direction. The flowers of the symmetrically located parts of the clothes should be in the same place. Clothes made of fabrics such as bobrik, velvet, semi-velvet, chiyudhoba should have the pile of all parts facing up, otherwise the areas of clothing that rub a lot will shine. If the hair of the gazelle is long and is combed in one direction, it should be cut so that the hairs hang down when the clothes are ready.

Pieces of clothing with sewing construction should be precisely cut so that no additional trimming or smoothing is required in the subsequent work process. For this, when placing the patterns, a gap of 0.5 cm should be left between the hem of the sleeves, the shoulder cut of the front part and the back part, and the front collar and other parts. There should be as little deviation as possible (no deviation at all is better). When the patterns are placed, it is not allowed to have any folds in the lining of the garment. The patterns of the front and back parts of the garment should be extremely precise along the weaving threads.

When cutting pieces of trousers, you can give a goat to the mouth. The side line is placed in the direction of the thread.

The templates are chalked after they are placed on the gazalama. The thickness of the chalk line should not exceed 1-2 mm.

The gauze intended for cutting is inspected, defects are identified, it is decaterated (sprayed with water or moistened) and ironed.

Table 2.

Patterns of pieces of women's national jackets and trousers the amount of tax to be imposed

Piece symbol	Section name	The name of the cut.	The value of seam allowance, cm.
01.	Front	Neck	0,8÷1,0

	coquette.	Let's eat	1,0
		Coquettish undercut	1,0
		Shoulder cut	1,0
		Board cutting (implantation).	0,7÷0,8
02.	Back coquette.	Neck	0,8÷1,0
		Let's eat	1,0
		Coquettish undercut	1,0
03, 04.	Front and back hem.	Shoulder cut	1,0
		Let's eat	1,0
		How to connect a coquette	1,0
		Side cut	1,0÷1,5
05.	sleeve	Cut the hem	3÷4
		Sleeve uprising	1,0
		Side cut	1,0
06.	Collar	Sleeve end	3,0
		Collar ends	0,7÷0,8
		It's a shame to tie the collar	0,8÷1,0

TECHNOLOGICAL MAP ON "MAKING NATIONAL DRESS AND ACCESSORIES PATTERNS"

Activities based on technology	Drawing	The procedure for performing the operation based on the standard
I	III	IV
1. Transfer the dress and necessary parts from the construction drawing	Pic.1	Each piece of the dress and the garment is drawn (copied) separately from the construction drawing using a tracing paper or using tape. In this case, the key and internal main structural lines of each section are also moved. The model design of the national dress and accessories was

<p>2. Determining the method of technological processing of shirts and accessories</p>	<p>look at the module.</p>	<p>developed in the T-33 module. The assembly drawing of the shirt and the garment and the scheme of processing the main technological nodes are studied. Used tools and equipment are shown.</p>
<p>3. Put the seam allowance values from the drawing of the back part patterns (coquette and hem).</p>		<p>Seam values are selected depending on the technological processing method and material properties. In flexible gas, the seam allowance is 1-5 mm more. The width of the main connecting seams is 1 cm, the seam allowance for turning the hem and the end of the sleeves is 3-4 cm. The seam allowance values are placed along the contours of the copied part and the contours of the templates are drawn.</p>
<p>4. Putting the seam allowance value on the pattern drawing of the front piece (coquette and hem)</p>		<p>The width of the main connecting seams is 1 cm, the seam allowance for turning the hem and the end of the sleeves is 3-4 cm. The seam allowance values are placed along the contours of the copied part and the contours of the template are drawn.</p>

shape of the lower collar, each upper collar is separately defined from the opposite side and cut flat. The lower collar is placed with the right side up and the upper collar is placed on top of it with the right side facing down, and its cuts are aligned with the cuts of the lower collar. It is stitched with a 0.7 cm wide overturned stitch on all three sides.

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